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Review Article

THE IMPORTANCE OF RECORDING THE INITIAL INFORMATION AND DATA OF THE INJURED WHILE PERFORMING FIRST AID: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract:

Objective: The timely and accurate recording of initial information during first aid plays a pivotal role in ensuring effective emergency care and improving patient outcomes. This systematic review explores the importance of documenting initial data, such as vital signs, injury details, and incident context, and its impact on subsequent medical interventions.

Methods: A comprehensive search was conducted across major databases, including PubMed, EMBASE, and Cochrane Library, for peer-reviewed studies published between 2016 and 2024. Studies were included if they focused on the role of initial information recording during first aid and its implications for patient outcomes. Data extraction and quality assessment followed PRISMA guidelines.

Results: Twenty studies met the inclusion criteria. Findings indicate that systematic recording of initial information during first aid significantly improves diagnostic accuracy, treatment planning, and overall patient survival rates. Barriers to effective data recording include lack of training, stress among responders, and absence of standardized protocols. Digital tools and structured forms were highlighted as effective solutions to improve the process.

Conclusion: The systematic recording of initial information is critical for the effectiveness of first aid and subsequent medical care. Training programs and the integration of technology in first aid protocols can enhance the accuracy and efficiency of data collection. Future research should focus on evaluating the implementation of standardized recording systems in diverse emergency settings.

Keywords: First Aid, Initial Information Recording, Emergency Care, Patient Outcomes, Systematic Review.

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INTRODUCTION

The immediate care provided during emergencies, commonly referred to as first aid, plays a vital role in stabilizing patients and preventing further complications until professional medical assistance arrives. Effective first aid is not solely about the physical interventions performed but also about the accurate recording of initial information, which includes the patient's vital signs, the nature and extent of injuries, and the circumstances of the incident. This initial data is crucial for informing subsequent medical decisions and ensuring continuity of care (Dinsmore et al., 2019).

In emergency scenarios, first responders and laypersons are often under significant stress, which can compromise the accuracy and completeness of recorded information. Despite this challenge, studies have demonstrated that systematically documenting initial data can significantly enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve patient outcomes (Cremonesi et al., 2018). For instance, data such as time of injury, observed symptoms, and immediate care measures taken can guide paramedics and emergency room staff in making timely and effective decisions.

Moreover, gaps in the recording of initial information have been identified as a critical barrier to effective first aid. Research suggests that the absence of standardized protocols for data recording during emergencies leads to inconsistencies, which can delay or hinder medical interventions (Tan et al., 2021). Addressing these gaps is essential to improving first aid practices and outcomes.

Recent advancements in technology have introduced digital tools that facilitate the accurate recording and transmission of data in emergency settings. However, their implementation remains inconsistent across regions and contexts, particularly in low-resource settings where training and access to resources are limited (Hunziker et al., 2019).

This systematic review aims to examine the importance of recording initial information during first aid and its impact on patient outcomes. By synthesizing the existing literature, we seek to highlight best practices, identify barriers, and propose actionable recommendations to enhance first aid protocols globally.

METHODS:

This systematic review followed PRISMA guidelines to ensure transparency and rigor in study selection and analysis. A comprehensive search was conducted across electronic databases, including PubMed, EMBASE, Cochrane Library, and Scopus, for peer-reviewed articles published between 2016 and 2024. Search terms included "first aid," "initial information recording," "emergency care," and "patient outcomes," combined with Boolean operators to refine results.

Studies were included if they examined the role of recording initial information during first aid and its impact on patient outcomes, emergency response efficiency, or care quality. Exclusion criteria comprised non-peer-reviewed articles, studies without empirical data, or those focused on unrelated aspects of first aid.

Two independent reviewers screened titles and abstracts, followed by full-text assessments for eligibility. Disagreements were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer. Data were extracted using a standardized template, capturing study characteristics (e.g., design, population, outcomes) and key findings.

The methodological quality of included studies was assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool and the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for observational studies. Data synthesis involved a narrative approach, highlighting thematic insights and trends. Where appropriate, meta-analytical techniques were applied

to quantify findings and assess heterogeneity across studies.

RESULTS:

The systematic review identified 1,500 articles through comprehensive database searches. After screening titles and abstracts, 150 full-text articles

were reviewed for eligibility. Of these, 25 studies met the inclusion criteria and were analyzed. The studies ranged from 2016 to 2024, reflecting an increasing focus on the importance of recording initial information during first aid. The number of studies addressing this topic showed a steady rise over the years, as depicted in Figure 1, indicating growing recognition of its relevance in emergency care.

Figure 1: Study inclusion over time.

The included studies represented diverse contexts, including urban, rural, and low-resource settings. Research designs varied, with observational studies forming the majority and interventional studies comprising the remainder. Participants in the studies ranged from lay responders to healthcare professionals, with sample sizes varying widely.

The findings demonstrated a consistent association between systematic recording of initial information and improved patient outcomes. This practice contributed to enhanced diagnostic accuracy, more efficient emergency responses, and better survival rates. Patient outcomes improved progressively, with advancements in practice and tools, as illustrated in Figure 2. The studies highlighted significant challenges in effective data recording, such as inadequate training, stress among first responders, and a lack of standardized protocols. These barriers were particularly pronounced in low-resource settings, where consistent documentation practices were more challenging to implement.

Figure 2: Patient outcome improvements linked to data recording.

Over the study period, there was a notable increase in the adoption of digital tools to aid in data recording. Tools such as mobile applications and wearable devices showed significant promise in improving data accuracy and accessibility. The use of these technologies rose sharply, particularly in the latter years of the review period, as depicted in Figure 3. Despite this progress, their adoption remains inconsistent globally, with significant disparities between high- and low-resource regions.

Figure 3: Adoption of Digital Tools in Data Recording

Geographic and contextual differences were evident in the reviewed studies. High-income countries demonstrated higher levels of data recording efficiency due to better infrastructure, training, and access to technology. In contrast, low-income and rural areas faced significant hurdles, emphasizing the

need for targeted interventions and resource allocation to improve practices in these settings.

The synthesis of evidence underscored the transformative potential of recording initial information during first aid. The practice not only improves immediate response capabilities but also has

far-reaching implications for patient outcomes and healthcare efficiency. While digital tools offer promising solutions, addressing systemic barriers remains critical to realizing their full potential. This review highlights the need for continued research and investment in standardized training and protocols to ensure effective data recording across diverse emergency scenarios.

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this systematic review highlight the critical importance of recording initial information during first aid and its significant impact on patient outcomes and emergency response efficiency. The studies reviewed consistently demonstrated that systematic documentation of vital signs, injury details, and incident context enhances diagnostic accuracy and facilitates timely medical interventions. This underscores the role of first responders not only in providing immediate physical care but also in ensuring the accurate relay of essential information to healthcare providers.

One of the most striking observations was the steady improvement in patient outcomes linked to effective data recording practices. Over the years, increased awareness and the adoption of structured approaches have contributed to these positive trends. However, the review also revealed persistent barriers that hinder effective data recording. Training gaps were a recurring issue, particularly in low-resource settings where access to educational programs for first responders is limited. Stress and time constraints further compound the problem, leading to incomplete or inaccurate documentation during emergencies.

The introduction of digital tools has been a transformative development in this field. Mobile applications and wearable devices have not only improved the accuracy and efficiency of data recording but also enabled real-time transmission of information to medical teams. However, the uneven adoption of these technologies points to systemic disparities. High-income countries have been quicker to integrate digital tools, while low-income regions face challenges such as lack of access, high costs, and insufficient training for using these technologies. Addressing these disparities will be crucial to achieving equitable improvements in first aid practices globally.

Another critical insight from the review is the need for standardized protocols for data recording. The absence of uniform guidelines has resulted in inconsistencies

in the quality and type of information recorded, which can adversely affect subsequent medical care. Developing and implementing standardized forms or checklists, tailored to diverse emergency contexts, could significantly enhance the consistency and reliability of recorded data.

Geographical and contextual variations in the studies highlight the importance of localized solutions. In rural and low-resource settings, tailored interventions such as community-based training programs and low-cost digital tools could address unique challenges. Conversely, in high-income areas, the focus could be on refining existing systems and ensuring their integration into broader emergency response frameworks.

The findings also have implications for policy and training. Policymakers must prioritize investment in training programs that emphasize the importance of data recording and equip first responders with the skills to document information accurately under pressure. Integrating these practices into first aid certification programs and workplace training can create a standardized baseline of competency. Furthermore, fostering partnerships between technology developers and healthcare systems can facilitate the broader adoption of digital tools, particularly in resource-limited areas.

This review has several limitations. The heterogeneity of the studies included, in terms of settings, populations, and methodologies, presents challenges for generalizing the findings. Additionally, most studies focused on specific regions or high-income countries, which may limit the applicability of conclusions to low-resource settings. Future research should aim to address these gaps by exploring innovative and context-specific strategies to improve data recording during first aid across diverse environments.

In conclusion, this review reinforces the critical role of recording initial information during first aid in improving patient outcomes and emergency care efficiency. While promising advancements, such as digital tools, offer new opportunities, addressing systemic barriers and developing standardized protocols are essential for maximizing their potential. By investing in training, technology, and tailored interventions, healthcare systems can ensure that the benefits of systematic data recording are realized across all contexts.

CONCLUSION:

This systematic review underscores the vital role of recording initial information during first aid in enhancing patient outcomes and the overall effectiveness of emergency care. Accurate and systematic documentation of key data, such as vital signs, injury specifics, and incident details, not only improves diagnostic accuracy but also ensures seamless communication between first responders and medical teams.

The findings highlight significant advancements in data recording practices over the years, particularly with the integration of digital tools. These technologies have demonstrated their potential to enhance data accuracy and accessibility, facilitating timely interventions. However, their uneven adoption globally reveals persistent disparities, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to bridge these gaps, particularly in low-resource settings.

Challenges such as inadequate training, high-stress environments, and the absence of standardized protocols continue to hinder the consistent recording of initial information. Addressing these barriers is crucial for improving first aid practices and ensuring equitable outcomes across diverse contexts. Standardized forms, structured training programs, and accessible digital tools are key interventions that can drive progress in this area.

Future research should focus on exploring innovative solutions to enhance data recording practices, particularly in underserved regions. By prioritizing training, technology integration, and standardized approaches, healthcare systems can optimize the critical role of first aid in saving lives and improving patient care pathways.

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